
Odonymic Analysis of Street Names in Lumwana Mine Township in Kalumbila, Zambia

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ABSTRACT

This article presents onomastics in the subfield of odonymics. It aims to odonymically analyse street names by identifying the street names; establishing the underlying factors that influenced street naming; and analysing the sociocultural significance of the street names in Lumwana Mine Township in Kalumbila. The analysis is guided by the critical toponymies theory which advances the intricate intersections of language, power, identity, and space in street names. The qualitative approach, with a case study design, underpins this study. Using snowball sampling, the study collected nine (9) street names and sampled five (5) participants (township officials and residents) as primary sources of data. Data were collected through in-depth interviews using interview guides and document analysis. The results indicate that streets were renamed at some point when there were some changes at the township management level. The new street names were formulated based on environmental affinity, and anglicisation. The study further shows that the street names were arrived at using various morphological processes including borrowing and clipping. The concept of street names does not only give the identity of the streets but also goes further to present the sociopolitical structure of the area. Notably, all the streets are anglicized and used with the regional language. While the mine is run by a non-Zambian company, the street names are coined using knowledge from the immediate environment using the regional language which promotes a sense of belonging and appreciation for local culture since the township serves as a campsite comprising residents from different parts of the country and the world at large. The study concludes that street names play a critical role in showing the language landscape, power, identity, and space of people inhabiting an area.

KEYWORDS: *Onomastics, odonymics, Lumwana Township, Social semiotics, stratification.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

This paper presents odonymics as a subfield of onomastics. It aims to odonymically analyse street names in Lumwana Mine Township in the Kalumbila District of Zambia. The study identifies the street names; establishes the underlying factors that influenced street naming; and analyses the sociocultural significance of the street names in the district under study.

According to Masule (2020), odonymics is the study of street names. The concept of naming streets is a vital one in the context of municipal councils and other local forms of administration. This is because it facilitates the easy location of places as well as the provision of some services. Street names or odonyms are not just signposts but may have some background to culture and social forces in the community where they are used. Such a background reflects the social, political, and cultural ideologies maintained by the colonial legacy among other forces (Wakumelo et al., 2016).

This study was conducted in Lumwana Mine Township, a mining area owned by non-Zambians and typically multilingual, multicultural, and multi-national. The township was established between 2006 and 2007 by the then owners, Equinox Mining, and later changed to Barrick Gold Mining who are the current owners. The study area has approximately 1500 residents, including adult men, women, and children. It started as a campsite solely for housing miners with the intent of establishing a new town in the province. Later on, the families started settling there and facilities such as schools were eventually introduced. It being initially a campsite culminated in the multilingual language situation. This is because the proprietor's policies do not discriminate in terms of who gets employment based on nationality, gender, or race in their establishment.

With the establishment of the township, a need arose for the streets to be named in the period during and immediately after the construction works were completed, and the then township administration decided to name the main road distinctively, while the other roads were named based on the geographical direction. The street names included: Spine, South Roads 1 and 2, North Roads

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1, 2, 3 and 4, and South-West 1, 2 and 3. However, at some point, with management changes, a decision was taken to change the street names. The new street names are the ones currently displayed at strategic points in the township.

Onomastics as a field has not been a popular field until recently hence the scarcity of studies conducted in this field. Worth noting is that several studies have been conducted globally, regionally, and locally in the hope of unravelling the various aspects of naming.

Chilala & Hang'ombe (2020) in their study examine eponymic place names in Zambia, specifically focusing on names of international airports and national stadia. It focuses on the names of places that were changed and how the doubled nature of these names was changed by the Patriotic Front regime in entrenching their political stamina. The study used the Critical Toponymies Theory which considers place names as social artifacts which are caught up in a web of social conflict, implicating key players in the place naming process as (re)producing unequal socio-political power balance, an aspect which can be viewed as a social problem.

The studies conducted in Zambia including that of Chilala & Hang'ombe (2020) concentrated on several aspects of naming in other regions of the country. However, onomastic studies in the Northwestern province of Zambia, particularly on street names are rare. This study odonymically analyses street names of the Lumwana Mine Township of Kalumbila district in the North-western Province of Zambia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have been conducted in line with onomastics in the recent past. From a global to a local perspective, some of the studies are reviewed as follows.

Globally, studies such as those Jaroslav (2013), and Helleland et al. (2012) among others have been conducted in the area of onomastics while a few have addressed toponomastics and they are reviewed as follows. Jaroslav's (2013) study focused on street names which he referred to as urbanonyms. In this study, the main aim was to assess the problems involved in understanding urbanonymy in modern cities from a new angle. The study used city maps and archival documents as sources of data. The findings were that the sampled urbanonymy (street names and square names) were commemorative in that they were mostly inspired by the personal names of those politicians and artists who were perceived positively as inspirational leaders and figures. Further, other names were found to be eclectic motivated.

Jaroslav (2013) also established that at the end of the 1980s, the street and city names changed. In line with this act, the changes can be described as merely cosmetic. Later on, many streets were renamed, however, the former enthusiasm for modelling and forming spaces via street names had seemingly gone. In addition, renaming streets and cities presented a very complex challenge to local authorities, and the action faced made it challenging for the local people as there was a lack of knowledge of the personalities commemorated among other aspects. The study by Jaroslav (2013) gives insights that are related to the current study as it concerned itself with street naming and the outcome of changing street and city names. This study informed the current study as regards the findings while it is significantly different from the current study in the methodological aspect. Notably, the study under review relied on document analysis and purposive sampling, the current study used snowball sampling.

Helleland et al. (2012) as cited by Masule (2020) conducted a study focused on 'Names and identities'. Their study aimed to show how names are identity bearers and identity markers. As a subfield of toponymics, they argued that there is an intimate relationship between place and place name, and discussed how place names reflect or give rise to feelings of individual and collective identity. They further concentrated on the meaning and function of place names, their role as links to the past, and their identity-building capacity. Masule (2020) established that names are not only linguistic expressions referring to an object in the real or imagined world but they are also symbols that bring about a variety of feelings depending on the relationship between the name user and the named object. It further established that place names are not only a source of linguistic knowledge, but also of geographical, historical, anthropological, ethnographic, social, and psychological knowledge.

The current study does recognize the contribution made by Helleland et al. (2012) in their study. Most notably, their study points out the functions and roles of place names as links to the past. It also suggests that place names possess hidden social and cultural aspects that influence the naming of places. The current study benefited the current study in the analysis of data and the subsequent discussion.

Rusu (2021) conducted a study under the title; Street naming practices: A systematic review of urban toponymic scholarship. The paper aimed at taking stock of the growing literature on street naming processes. The study was quantitative and it provides a meta-analytical systematic review of odonymic scholarship. The study involved a collection of 121 peer-reviewed articles on street names published in English language academic journals in the social sciences and the humanities as identified in the Scopus database. The study established that the statistical analyses conducted on these materials indicate (1) the temporal dynamics of knowledge production and the geographical hotspots in toponomastic scholarship, (2) the geopolitical settings and historical contexts framing these studies, (3) the theoretical perspectives employed to conceptualise street naming practices, and (4) the methodological outlines characterising the research done on street names in the literature. The conclusions point out four main clusters of toponomastic research and indicate directions for future inquiry in street name scholarship.

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The study by Rusu (2021) contributes to the broader spectrum of literature in the field of onomastics. However, while it focused on the statistics involving studies in this field and was qualitative, the current study focused on a specific field of onomastics – odonymics - and takes the qualitative approach for a more detailed understanding of what is obtained in the field.

Deploying onomastics, semiotics, and interpretative approach to translation, text analysis, and cultural studies, Oha et al. (2017) in their study entitled; *On Nigerian and Indian Toponyms: Socio-Cultural Divergence and Development*, selected one hundred (100) toponyms from different parts of India and Nigeria and analysed them to show the development of place-names in both countries in the new millennium. It was established that in Nigeria, the influence of British English is everywhere in the names of cities, towns, villages, streets, tourist centers, and rivers, including ‘Douglas Road’, ‘Wetheral Road’, ‘Owerri’ instead of ‘Owere’, ‘Awka’ instead of ‘Oka’, ‘Warri instead of ‘Wori,’ among others. In India, however, we see indigenized naming forms such as ‘Tilak Nagar’, ‘Mahavir Nagar’, ‘Rama Krishna Ashram Marg’, and ‘Rajiv Chowk’. English language in India is fast dying, while in Nigeria, the reverse is the case. It was further concluded that while India is making serious efforts towards complete linguistic independence, through the development of place names, Nigeria is promoting anglicised place- names, which is detrimental to the development of Indigenous Nigerian languages. The study of Oha et. al. (2017) is significant to the current study as it addresses several similar issues addressed by the current study. The study under review considers the main forces behind the names and how people have reacted over time to those forces. The findings informed the discussion of the findings in the current study.

From the African perspective, studies such as those by Okal (2018) and Filani & Melafa (2014) are among the studies in the field of onomastics. The study by Okal (2018) explores patronyms under the title; ‘A linguistic overview of the patronymic and gender names amongst the selected African communities.’ The study used a descriptive design. The data was collected through document analysis, application of critical observation and non-formal interviews. Participants were purposively sampled and the names sampled were morphologically analysed. The findings reveal that children are given first and second names, and later on add the third name, which is normally that of the father. However, there are instances whereby free morphs are added before the father’s name is mentioned. This is normally added for self-exaltation and thus should be considered facultative. Further, it established that there are also gender names that tend to have specific prefixes to denote either males or females. The study by Okal (2018) is related to the current study in that it belongs to the onomastics field. However, though it is not concerned with odonyms, the current study benefited from its methodological aspect.

Filani & Melafa (2014) in their paper titled ‘A Socio-semiotic Study of Nicknaming among Undergraduates in a Nigerian University’ focused on nicknaming as a signification tool for identity reinvention from a socio-semiotic dimension. Data in their study were sampled purposively from students' halls of residence at the University of Ibadan. They were further analysed using the socio-semiotic theory of sign. It was established that the use of irony in names was a common tool for reinvention, especially in instances where the nicknames were given as derogatory labels to redesign the identities of the affected individuals. It was further established that others use nicknames to project a sense of reinvented self, especially in instances where the nicknames were the creations of the individuals concerned. The study is related to the current study in that it attempts the holistic approach to literature, it concerned itself mainly with nicknaming, a sub-category of personal names. While the current study went on to look at another sub-category of Toponymics. It also considers the critical toponymic theory as opposed to the socio-semiotics theory of sign used in the study under review.

Tan & Purschke’s (2021) paper with the title; *Street Name Changes as Language and Identity Inscription in the Cityscape*, examines the role of language selection in constructing the cityscape of highly multilingual, postcolonial places like Malaysia and Namibia. They suggest that the relationship between language policy, the construction of a national identity, and linguistic inscriptions in the cityscape can be seen as part of language planning. Their paper focuses on street names as typical targets of language policy. Using contrastive data and methodology, the duo analysed the renegotiation of postcolonial cityscapes in Kuala Lumpur (historical city centre, map data, large period) and Windhoek (entire cityscape, newspaper reports, short period). Their study established that a notion of how the cityscape as a complex socio-symbolic text is being constantly rewritten by its actors. They found that several motives were attached to the process of naming such as cultural representation, national identity building, and ideological consolidation of the cityscape.

The paper by Tan & Purschke (2021) contributes to the body of literature on toponymics. The findings contributed to the discussion of the findings in of current study. However, there are differences in the methodological approach taken by the duo as compared to the one taken in the current study. The duo employed the contrastive data approach while the current study employed the case study approach.

In Zambia, there is limited literature in the field of onomastics as the field is relatively new. The following studies have been conducted so far. Hamoonga (2019) conducted a study entitled ‘An onomastic study of names in selected business houses of Livingstone town, Zambia’. At the core of Hamoonga’s study was to establish the different meanings associated with trade names and the nature of stylistic features used in selected business names of Livingstone Town concerning society. The study also aimed to examine how paralinguistic elements blended with the actual name tokens for meaning. The study under review was guided by four objectives; establishing how business names are formulated; identifying the linguistic features associated with name tokens; establishing how social actors represent their society’s social beliefs and value systems through business names and establishing

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how graphic information enhances the meanings or semantic values of business names. Data for this study were collected from four selected townships of Livingstone namely: Dambwa, the Town centre area, Libuyu, and Maramba. To achieve the objectives, the study collected a total of 160 names for analysis.

Hamoonga's (2019) study used the Bourdieuan theoretical framework of Habitus to analyse data. The study reveals that the names of the business houses sampled mainly originated from the use of nicknames seen as the main theme. In addition, establishment names originated from clan names, complexion, circumstances surrounding one's birth, and religious attachment. Further, the study established business names were morphologically classified into two categories including those created through such morphological processes as blending, acronyms, clipping, compounding, initialism, and reduplication. Ultimately, the study under review concluded that business names offer opportunities for owners to communicate important information that deals with society.

The study by Hamoonga (2019) is related to the current study in that it also considers the morphological aspect of establishment names. However, it did not consider street names while the current study concentrates on street naming practices. Further, the study under review employs the Bourdieuan theoretical framework of Habitus while the current study employs critical onomastics theoretical and lexical morphological frameworks for a clear understanding of the naming practices in the study area.

Another study conducted by Wakumelo et al. (2016) titled 'The Toponymics of post-colonial Zambia: Street naming patterns in Lusaka'. According to the findings, it was observed that not only did street names or odonyms form part of the address of business institutions or organisations located on the streets but also reflected the social, political, and cultural ideologies maintained by the name givers. With the thematic approach employed in the methodology to categorise the street names and the street naming practices of Lusaka city, the study collected and categorised street names. Among the themes categorised included: Botanic theme, Wildlife theme, symbolic and commemorative themes. The study concluded that most Zambian people were ignorant about the process, procedure, and value of street names and naming. This was attributed to the fact that there was no proper policy document to outline the process, procedures, and other issues related to street names and naming in Lusaka.

The study by Wakumelo et al. (2016) on place names and the naming systems of street names also called odonyms provides insights into the practice. The findings of the study under review inform the current study discussion of findings as it is most similar to the current study.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The analysis is guided by two theories; critical toponymies theory which advances the intricate intersections of language, power, identity, and space in street names, and the Lexical Morphology theoretical model.

3.1 Critical Toponymies Theory

Critical Toponymies Theory (CTT), a theory that re-politicises place names, was popularised in the 1990s. Some of the advocates of CTT are Myers (2009); Rose-Redwood & Alderman (2011); Rose-Redwood et al. (2010). The main argument in this theory is that place names are not neutral social artifacts. Rather, they can be used in harnessing the aspirations of the names in the toponymic landscape. This makes place naming a contested social practice. Since people do not have the same privileges as far as place names bestowal are concerned (Perko et al., 2017:103), those who are powerful politically or socially win the contest to nominate places. It follows then, that the names bestowed on places reflect their agenda, aspirations, version of the history, and conception of the world.

Among other aspects, place names can have an economic nuance (Light, 2014). In such an instance, place names may be attuned to the economic agenda of the bestower. Place names can also have a political penchant (Melissa & Kosuke, 2016), whereby the names are inclined toward the political aspirations of the bestower which is referred to as political semiotics. In political semiotics, the names assigned to places may be those which celebrate or commemorate politicians or at least, reflect the ideologies of the government. Scalar is yet another aspect reflected in place names (Hagen, 2011). Scalar can have to do with the selection of a place name guided by whether the place is of (inter)national significance or not. If a place is of (inter)national significance, for example, the place can be bestowed a name that also attracts (inter)national visibility.

CTT was applied in the analysis of the motive behind naming as well as the renaming of streets in Lumwana Mine Township. Since it is concerned with how various players in power positions exercise their power as they reflect their agenda, aspirations, version of the history, and conception of the world, it was most appropriate for the current study.

3.2 Lexical Morphology

Lexical morphology is a theoretical model that was proposed by Pesetsky (1979) and further expanded by Kiparsky (1982). This model is mainly concerned with the lexicon, and when morphologically analysed comprises the lexemes in a language. This a theory, it is concerned with word formation, derivation, and compounding (Masule, 2020).

In light of the current study, this theory was applied in the analysis of the various word formation processes that the name bestowers used when naming the streets of Lumwana Mine Township in Kalumbila.

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4. METHODOLOGY

The qualitative approach, with a case study design, underpins this study. Where according to Kombo & Tromp (2006), a research design “is the framework of research methods and techniques selected by a researcher” after a comprehensive analysis of all the available ones. A research design is simply an overall strategy the researcher chooses in the integration of the different components of the study coherently and logically, thereby, ensuring that the researcher effectively addresses the research problem (Siame, 2019; Siame & Banda, 2021).

As cited in Mvula (2017), Windridge (2007: 6), posits that qualitative research is not just an alternative to quantitative research, rather, it is a different approach that allows the researcher to ask and answer different kinds of questions. This study used in-depth interviews and document analysis methods (Siame, 2022). The participants were sampled using the snowball sampling technique. Altogether, the study used nine (9) street names, and five (5) township officials as primary sources of data.

According to Kombo & Tromp (2006), the analysis of data can be done qualitatively, quantitatively, or using the mixed methods approach. Under each approach are several ways of analyzing data. In qualitative studies, some of the approaches in data analysis include; inductively and deductively. Under the two approaches, thematic analysis is prominent which allows the researcher to categorize the collected data into themes (Siame & Banda, 2024a, 2024b). Therefore, data in this study were analysed thematically by the revelation of themes in the study.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the data collected, six major themes emerged, namely; Street names, etymology of street names, morphological structure and standardization of the street names, factors that influenced the naming and renaming of streets, multilingualism and street naming, and sociocultural significance of the street names.

5.1 Street Names

The table below shows the former and current streets, lanes, and avenue names in Lumwana Mine Township in Zambia:

Table 1: Street Names

S/N	NAME	FORMERLY
01	Mubanga Drive	Spine
02	Mweenge lane	South Road 2
03	Katenge Avenue	South West 3
04	Bitachi Avenue	South West 2
05	Kapwi Avenue	South West 1
06	Kifumbe street	North Road 1
07	Bilalo street	North Road 2
08	Lweo street	North Road 2
09	KiSokoto street	North Road 4

Table 1 shows the street names currently being used in Lumwana Mine Township. The study collected a total of nine (9) street names from the research site. Linguistically, the street names used in the research site were mainly characterized by two (2) languages; kiiKaonde and English.

5.2 Etymology of Street Names

The table below shows the meanings attached to the street names in Lumwana Mine Township:

Table 2: Etymology of street names

S/N	NAME	ETYMOLOGY
01	Mubanga Drive	Hardwood Tree
02	Mweenge lane	An Indigenous tree that produces white gum and under it, initiation ceremonies for girls are conducted.
03	Katenge Avenue	Small piece of cloth (wrapper)
04	Bitachi Avenue	Indigenous tree (Kitachi) that grows on hills and its leaves are eaten as vegetables.
05	Kapwi Avenue	Indigenous fruit tree (Kapwi)
06	Kifumbe street	Indigenous fruit tree – with powdered fruits (Bifumbe)
07	Bilalo street	Indigenous grass that grows beside rivers and is used to make mats for sleeping on
08	Lweo street	Grass for thatching reeds
09	Kisokoto street	Hardwood timber used for making furniture

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Table 2 presents the etymological aspect of the street names in Lumwana Mine Township. The study established that most of the streets were de-nominals. This implies that all the street names in Table 2 are derived from common nouns and bestowed as proper nouns of streets. For example:

1. Kapwi Avenue
2. Bilalo Street

Examples 1 and 2 show how the name bestowers transformed common nouns into proper nouns used as street names. Etymologically, 1 is a name of an indigenous fruit tree while 2 is a type of indigenous grass used in the making of sleeping mats.

5.3 Morphological Structure and Standardization of the Street Names

The study established that morphologically, all the street names in Lumwana Mine Township were compound nouns. In their compound form, they are made up of a local and an English word. This is similar to the findings of Hamoonga (2019) whose study established that bestowers of names, be they street or business names use morphological processes such as compounding. Notably, all the assigned street names have the local name followed by the generic standardized name in English.

Generally, some of the common generic parts of street names are presented in the table below:

Table 3: Generic parts of street names

S/N	GENERIC PART	MEANING
01	Lane	Street, with trees on both sides, flower beds, and lawns that allow for the passage of vehicles and walkers into a garden, a park, or wood.
02	Street	Local public roads part of the local network
03	Alley	Small narrow road
04	Square	Exposed small or large open public space in a city or village, usually surrounded by public buildings, where several streets or avenues would end, and where frequently commercial, festive, or public events are held
05	Intersection	Intersection point with obligatory driving direction
06	Lane	Public country road
07	Boulevard	Major artery of the road network that links several town sectors
08	Avenue	Artery of the road network that serves as a collector. This artery would provide access to the local streets.
09	Promenade	Road especially adapted for promenaders

Source: <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/ungegn/pubs/documents/Training%20Manual.pdf>

Table 3 shows some of the generic parts that are used in street naming as indicated in the United Nations' Toponymy Training Manual. It is worth noting that some of the generic parts used are sometimes used interchangeably in some countries while in others, they may not be reflective of what is obtained.

In line with Table 3, the study found that the street names in Lumwana Mine Township were not exempted from the use of generic parts in the street names. For example;

3. Mweenge Lane
4. Kapwi Avenue
5. Kifumbe Street

Figure 1: Street Sign (BITACHI AVENUE)

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Figure 2: Street sign (KISOKOTO STREET)

Figure 3: Street sign (KATENGE AVENUE)

Figure 4: Street sign (MWEENGE LANE)

Examples, 3, 4, 5, and Figures 1, 2, 3, and 4 show how the name bestowers used the generic parts in the naming of the streets in Lumwana Mine Township. It must also be stated that some generic parts used on some street names do not reflect the description as indicated in Table 3 above and some parts were used interchangeably.

For example:

6. Kifumbe Street
7. Mweenge Lane

Figure 4: Street sign (BILALO STREET)

Examples 6, 7, and Figure 4 are typical of the interchangeable use of the generic part. In this case, the two streets possess the same characteristics. In addition, the study noted that the use of the generic part; 'Avenue' was adhered to by the name bestowers of the street names in Lumwana Mine Township.

5.4 Factors that Influenced the Naming and Renaming of Streets

In general, several factors influence naming practices in each society. The study established two main factors that influenced the naming and renaming of streets in Lumwana Mine Township.

5.4.1 Geographical Affinity

The study established that the main factor that influenced the naming of the streets immediately after the establishment of the township was geographical. This influence implies that the name bestowers wanted to give directions in the way the streets were named. For example;

8. South Road 1
9. North Road 2
10. South West 1

In examples; 8, 9, 10, and 11, the bestowers used geographical nouns to name the streets. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Masule (2020) who also established that naming can be influenced by such factors as geographical affinity.

5.4.2 Environmental Affinity/ Indigenization

In the renaming of the streets, the study established that the major factor that influenced the renaming of the streets of Lumwana Mine Township was environmental affinity /indigenization. Indigenization refers to the process by which name bestowers bestow names on establishments that are meant to connect the organization, and streets to the immediate environment while cultivating a sense of belonging. Especially prompted by the coming in of the new administration, it was resolved that the street names be renamed using Indigenous names. The sole purpose of adopting indigenous names was to enhance the sense of belonging to the residents. Notably, as in table two, all the street names that were assigned after the change were derived from local things and the environment. This finding is in line with the findings of Masule (2020) who found that establishments such as Radio Stations are sometimes named for indigenization purposes. In addition, this finding further justifies the views of Oha et al. (2017) who argue that local names could act as primordial evidence of the language of the local People. This therefore helps to preserve the language and culture of such people. Wakumelo et al. (2016), also found similar results where their study found themes including the botanic theme of street names and agreed that the name bestowers exercise their power and ideologies through the names they give as evident in the renaming of the street names of Lumwana Mine Township.

5.4.3 Anglicisation

In addition to the factors above, the study established that anglicisation was also one of the factors that influenced the naming of streets in Lumwana Mine Township. This concept refers to the process by which name bestowers bestow a name that has an English language affinity. In addition, anglicization serves as a way of maintaining the modernity of the names given. For example:

11. Kapwi Avenue

In example 11, the name bestower bestowed the name which consists of the English and kiiKaonde languages. In this sense, the two languages share equal status as regards their use in street naming. This finding coincides with Oha et al. (2017) who

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discovered that in Nigeria, almost all the street names have an element of the English language while in India, and the opposite is the case. They further argue that the case of Nigeria is an indicator that the indigenous languages are under threat if the reverse action is not considered. Rusu's (2021) paper also found that anglicisation was a prominent feature in the naming of streets.

5.5 Multilingualism and Street Naming

Lumwana Mine Township stands out as one of the typical examples of multilingual communities in Zambia. This implies that it is home to many people from different backgrounds, ethnicities, and nationalities. While it was easy for the local administrators to name the streets of the township, the main challenge remains in the use of the new street names.

Notably, the study established that though the new street names have been displayed in strategic places, the residents prefer using the old street names. Among the reasons, the participants indicated that some residents did not know the languages used in the names later on their meanings. In addition, some residents indicated that the old street names were easier to say as compared to the new ones.

The aspect of multilingualism was noted by Tan & Purschke (2021) and their findings are similar to the findings of the current study. They established that especially in countries that have colonial history, the key actors strive to rewrite the signs in the cities by changing the names though the act is challenging in multilingual places. Further, they note that nations go to the extent of declaring the national language(s) while giving it a higher status than other languages. A situation similar to what is obtained in Lumwana Mine Township where the Regional Language, kiiKaonde, when it came to renaming the streets was given a higher status as compared to the other languages. Jaroslav's (2013) study also discovered the challenges associated with the renaming of the street and indicates that the process gives challenges to the local administration among other players.

5.6 Sociocultural Significance of the Street Names

The study found that the street names, especially the new street names were of social and cultural significance to the local people. One participant indicated that most of the names given to the streets were names of local fruits, vegetables, and materials used in the everyday life of the local people. The use of such gives the local people a sense of belonging and acceptance in that the streets are a reflection of their local culture and general way of life. This finding agrees with the findings by Tan & Purschke (2021).

The study found that the new street names were a great tool for cultural preservation and transmission from one generation to the other. Some participants indicated that the more the elders and the young ones looked at and used the street names, their culture was preserved and passed on to the younger generations. Oha et al. (2017) and Wakumelo et al. (2016), agreed with this finding reinforcing the idea that street names play a vital role in the preservation and transmission of culture.

6. CONCLUSION

The study identified the street names in Lumwana Mine Township and established that all the names were compound nouns predominantly made of two languages; kiiKaonde and English language. These street names in their compound form adhered to the adoption of the generic parts of street naming as per the custom in other places. Morphologically, the street names analysed used two processes; compounding and borrowing. Notably, the bestowers borrowed from the English language. The study concludes that several factors influence street naming and in the study area, Geographical affinity, Indigenisation, and Anglicization were the main factors that influenced the naming and renaming of the streets of Lumwana Mine Township. The study further highlights that multilingualism poses various challenges especially when there is a street renaming process. Socioculturally, the street names have significance in that they facilitate the preservation and transmission of the culture of the local people from generation to generation. It further gives the local people a sense of belonging and acceptance when they see their local language being used in the naming of the streets.

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